

Public Health Risks Associated with Indoor Air Quality in High-Patronage Restaurants in Owerri Metropolis.

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Abstract: Indoor air quality is an important public health concern, particularly in restaurants where high levels of human activity can promote the introduction and dispersion of microbial contaminants. This study assessed the influence of customer patronage on the indoor air microbial quality of selected restaurants in Owerri metropolis, Nigeria, and evaluated the associated public health implications. Twelve restaurants were investigated. Air samples were collected using the plate sedimentation technique, and microbial loads were determined in the presence and absence of human activities. Bacterial and fungal isolates were identified using standard cultural, microscopic, and biochemical test. The bacterial species identified were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Micrococcus luteus*. Fungal isolates included *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, and *Cladosporium fulvum*. Restaurants along the Owerri-Onitsha highway recorded significantly higher bacterial and fungal counts compared with those on World Bank road. The highest microbial loads were observed in a high-patronage restaurant along the highway, while the lowest counts occurred in a low-patronage restaurant on World Bank road. *Escherichia coli* and *Rhizopus stolonifer* were the most frequently isolated bacterial and fungal species, respectively. Microbial counts were minimal during sampling conducted shortly after cleaning and in the absence of customers, emphasizing the strong influence of human presence on indoor air quality. The detection of potentially pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms highlights possible health risks, particularly for immunocompromised individuals. Improved sanitation, adequate ventilation, and routine monitoring of indoor air quality are recommended to reduce microbial contamination and protect public health in restaurant environments.

Keywords: indoor air quality, customer patronage, restaurants, microbial load, public health

1. Introduction

Indoor air represents one of the most important environmental determinants of human health and is often a major source of exposure to contaminants. It typically contains a complex mixture of biological and non-biological particles, including dust-associated microorganisms (Airaksinen et al., 2004). Among these, microbial contaminants are of particular concern because of their potential pathogenicity and their ability to induce allergic reactions, exacerbate respiratory conditions, and cause other adverse health effects following inhalation (Benson, 2004). Due to their small size, airborne microorganisms can remain suspended for prolonged periods, with air currents facilitating their persistence and dissemination within enclosed environments.

Restaurants are public indoor environments where indoor air quality is strongly influenced by human occupancy and activity. Factors such as customer density, movement patterns, location of sanitary facilities, and frequency of interaction between food preparation and dining areas all contribute to microbial air contamination (Braun-Fahrlander & Lauener, 2003). Environmental parameters including

temperature, humidity, illumination, and nutrient availability further determine microbial survival and proliferation. Building dampness and moisture intrusion have been consistently associated with mould growth and a wide range of health outcomes, including asthma, allergic disorders, sick building syndrome, chronic respiratory infections, eye and skin irritation, and hypersensitivity pneumonitis (Filipiak, 2004).

Ventilation systems also play a crucial role in shaping indoor microbial concentrations. Mechanical ventilation systems are generally more effective than natural ventilation in filtering incoming air and removing contaminants, often resulting in microbial loads that are two to seven times lower than those observed in naturally ventilated buildings (Fox & Rosario, 1994; Inetianbor et al., 2014). Differences have also been reported among mechanical ventilation systems, with buildings equipped with mechanical supply and exhaust systems or air-handling units exhibiting lower microbial concentrations than those using fan-coil or exhaust-only systems (Lehtonen et al., 1993).

Human occupancy remains a major contributor to indoor microbial pollution.

Activities such as coughing, sneezing, talking, and movement can release large quantities of microorganisms into the air, where they may remain suspended for hours or days (Lignell et al., 2007). Consequently, environments with high visitor turnover, such as restaurants located along major highways, are particularly susceptible to elevated microbial contamination.

This study aimed to compare the indoor air quality of restaurants located along the high-traffic Owerri-Onitsha highway with those situated along World Bank road, which experiences relatively lower customer patronage. By assessing microbial load and diversity, the study sought to evaluate the public health implications of indoor air contamination in these environments.

2. Materials and Methods

Study Area

Owerri is a major transit city located in South-East Nigeria, situated at between latitudes 5°28'–5°30' N and longitudes 7°01'–7°03' E. Owing to its strategic position linking the South-South, South-East and North-Central regions of the country,

Owerri experiences intense commuter traffic. This has resulted in high patronage of restaurants and fast-food outlets, particularly along the Owerri-Onitsha highway. In contrast, World Bank road, another major road within Owerri metropolis, experiences comparatively lower customer traffic.

Sample Collection

Twelve restaurants were selected for the study: seven (A–G) along the Owerri-Onitsha highway and five (V–Z) along World Bank road. Air sampling was carried out using the plate sedimentation method to determine viable bacterial and fungal counts in the presence and absence of human activities (Nathanson, 1993). Duplicate sterile Petri dishes containing nutrient agar and Sabouraud dextrose agar were placed on the floor of each restaurant and exposed for 20 minutes during the afternoon period. Nutrient agar was used for culturable heterotrophic bacteria, while Sabouraud dextrose agar supported fungal isolation.

Microbial Isolation and Identification

Following exposure, plates were transported immediately to the laboratory. Nutrient agar plates were incubated at 37

°C for 18–24 h, while Sabouraud dextrose agar plates were incubated at 28 ± 2 °C and monitored daily for three days (Su et al., 2001; Sundell et al., 2002). Distinct colonies were sub-cultured to obtain pure isolates.

Fungal isolates were identified based on macroscopic and microscopic characteristics

following staining with lactophenol cotton blue (Parat et al., 1997; Udochukwu et al., 2015). Bacterial isolates were identified using standard biochemical tests, including citrate utilization, urease, catalase, indole, oxidase, and coagulase tests (Reponen et al., 1992; Reynolds et al., 1990).

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1. Total microbial count of the indoor air in the sampled restaurants along Owerri-Onitsha highway and World Bank road. (A) Bacterial count of the indoor air with restaurants B and Y having the highest and least count respectively. (B) Fungal count of the indoor air with restaurants B and Z having the highest and least count respectively

Figure 2. Distribution of isolated microbes in the sampled restaurants in Owerri metropolis. (A) Frequency of bacterial isolates with *Escherichia coli* with the highest distribution and *Streptococcus pyogenes* with the least distribution. (B) Frequency of fungal isolates with *Rhizopus stolonifer* with the highest distribution and *Clasdosporium fulvum* the least distributed.

Key: 1 = *Micrococcus luteus*, 2 = *Staphylococcus aureus*, 3 = *Bacillus subtilis*, 4 = *Escherichia coli*, 5 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 6 = *Streptococcus pyogenes*, a = *Aspergillus niger*, b = *Aspergillus flavus*, c = *Penicillium chrysogenum*, d = *Rhizopus stolonifer*, e = *Fusarium oxysporum*, f = *Clasdosporium fulvum*.

Table 1. Bacteria isolates from restaurants on Owerri-Onitsha high way

Isolates	V	W	X	Y	Z	F	G	% Frequency
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	71.40
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	100
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	57.10
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	100
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	42.90

Key: += Present and - = Absent.

Table 2. Bacteria isolates from restaurants on World Bank road

Isolates	V	W	X	Y	Z	% Frequency
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0.00
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+	+	-	+	-	60.00
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0.00
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	+	-	-	+	-	40.00
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	+	-	+	+	60.00
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-	-	-	-	20.00

Key: += Present and - = Absent.

Table 3. Fungal isolates from restaurants on Owerri-Onitsha high way

Isolates	V	W	X	Y	Z	X	G	% Frequency
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	71.40
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	57.10
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	57.10
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	100
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	57.10
<i>Clasdosporium fulvum</i>	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	28.60

Key: += Present and - = Absent

Table 4. Fungal isolates from restaurants on World Bank road

Isolates	V	W	X	Y	Z	% Frequency
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	-	-	-	+	-	20.00
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0.00
<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	+	-	-	+	-	40.00
<i>Rhizopus stolonifer</i>	-	-	-	-	+	20.00
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	-	+	+	-	-	40.00
<i>Clasdosporium fulvum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0.00

Key: += Present and - = Absent.

The assessment of indoor air quality revealed marked variations in microbial load among the

sampled restaurants. Restaurant B, located along the Owerri-Onitsha highway, recorded

the highest bacterial count (400 cfu/min), whereas restaurant Y on World Bank road exhibited the lowest count (25 cfu/min). A similar trend was observed for fungal contamination, with restaurant B recording the highest fungal load (6.0 cfu/min) and restaurant Z the lowest (1.5 cfu/min).

The dominant bacterial isolates were *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, while *Streptococcus pyogenes* was the least frequently detected. The predominance of Gram-positive cocci, commonly associated with human skin and mucosal surfaces, suggests that human presence was a major source of indoor air contamination. This observation aligns with earlier studies reporting higher concentrations of Gram-positive bacteria in indoor environments (Stark et al., 2003; Udochukwu et al., 2016b).

Among fungal isolates, *Rhizopus stolonifer* was the most prevalent, whereas *Cladosporium fulvum* was least distributed. Many of the isolated fungi, including *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, and *Rhizopus* species, are recognized opportunistic pathogens capable of inducing allergic reactions, asthma, rhinitis, and conjunctivitis, particularly in susceptible individuals (Udochukwu et al., 2016a; Walinder et al., 1997).

Microbial counts were negligible during sampling conducted shortly after cleaning and in the absence of customers, confirming the strong influence of human activities on indoor air microbiology. Restaurants along the Owerri-Onitsha highway consistently recorded higher microbial loads, reflecting their greater customer influx, particularly during peak hours (10:00 am–3:00 pm). Environmental factors such as building maintenance, sanitation practices, and temperature, humidity, and ventilation systems likely contributed to the observed differences (Reynolds et al., 1990; Shelton et al., Shelton et al., 2002). Overall, the findings highlight the public health risks associated with poor indoor air quality in overcrowded restaurants. Enhanced sanitation measures, improved ventilation, and effective crowd management are essential to reduce microbial contamination, prevent foodborne infections, and ensure a safer dining environment for customers.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that customer patronage and human activities significantly influence the microbial quality of indoor air in restaurants within Owerri metropolis. Restaurants located along the high-traffic Owerri-Onitsha highway consistently recorded higher bacterial and fungal loads compared

with those along World Bank road, which experience relatively lower customer influx. The isolation of potentially pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms, including *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Aspergillus* spp., *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Rhizopus stolonifer*, underscores the potential public health risks associated with prolonged exposure to contaminated indoor air, particularly among immunocompromised individuals, food handlers, and frequent customers. The markedly lower microbial counts observed during periods of minimal human presence highlight the central role of human occupancy in indoor air contamination. Variations in microbial load among restaurants further reflect the influence of sanitation practices, ventilation systems, and environmental conditions. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for strict hygiene enforcement, improved ventilation strategies, routine indoor air quality monitoring, and effective crowd management in restaurants, especially those with high customer turnover. Implementing these measures will not only reduce the risk of airborne and foodborne infections but also enhance consumer confidence and promote safer public eating environments.

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